

A Study on the Association of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus and Hypothyroidism Patients of Bhagalpur District, Bihar

Hemper Kumar¹, Varsha Sinha²

¹JR 3rd Year, Department of Biochemistry, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, Bhagalpur, Bihar.

²Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, Bhagalpur, Bihar.

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Corresponding author: Dr Varsha Sinha

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Abstract

Background: Insulin and thyroid hormones compete with one another for control of cellular metabolism. With this, it was intended for the study to determine the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in people with type 2 diabetes (DM) at Bhagalpur District.

Materials and Methods: From June 2021 to May 2022, research was carried out in the biochemistry department of Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital in Bhagalpur, Bihar. The study included all type 2 diabetics aged >30 years, regardless of therapy. Excluded from the study were anyone taking metformin, smoking, taking thyroid hormones, having thyroid surgery, receiving radioiodine therapy, being pregnant, and using steroids. Venous blood samples were collected to measure thyroid function estimated using the autoanalyzer, glycosylated haemoglobin, lipid profile, fasting blood glucose, and 2-hour post glucose blood sugar. Chi-square test was employed to assess variations in categorical variables, and a statistically significant value of $p < 0.05$ was chosen.

Results: Among 104 patients, 82.7% had normal thyroid function, 12.5% had subclinical hypothyroidism, and 4.8% had clinical hypothyroidism; when age and gender were connected, the difference was not statistically significant. However, there was a strong correlation with dyslipidemia.

Conclusion: People with type 2 diabetes frequently have hypothyroidism, which benefits everyone's metabolism.

Keywords: Diabetes, Thyroid, Thyroidism, Individual

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Background

The most prevalent endocrine condition, diabetes mellitus (DM), is characterised by persistent hyperglycemia brought on by deficiencies in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. The pathogenic processes that lead to the development of diabetes include defects that impair insulin function

as well as autoimmune death of pancreatic beta cells, which results in insulin shortage [1]. The main factor causing diabetes complications is hyperglycemia. The main reasons of the epidemic are sedentary lifestyle, varied dietary patterns, ethnicity, and genetic predisposition [2]. The second

most prevalent endocrine problem is thyroid disease, which is similarly frequent in the general population. As a result, it is typical for someone to have diabetes as well as thyroid illness [3]. Between 2.2 and 17% of diabetic patients were shown to have thyroid impairment in various studies' respective populations [4,5]. The prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in diabetes ranges from 31% to 46.5%, according to a small number of studies [6,7]. Insulin and thyroid hormones compete with one another in the cellular metabolism of lipids, proteins, and carbohydrates. If their levels change, thyroid hormone and insulin both experience functional impairment [8]. The release of TSH from the hypothalamus, which is where DM first appears to affect thyroid function, and the conversion of T4 to T3 in the peripheral tissues, which is where DM second appears to affect thyroid function. Low serum T3, an increase in reverses T3, variation in T4 levels, and a reversible decrease in T4 5'deiodinase activity and hepatic concentration is all effects of hyperglycemia [9]. Recognizing this interdependence between thyroid disease and diabetes is crucial for advising clinicians on how to treat both conditions as effectively as possible. To determine the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in type 2 DM, the study was designed with this goal in mind.

Material and Methods

This study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar from June 2021 to May 2022. In this study, random sampling was taken. All type 2 diabetics over the age of 30 were included in the study. Smokers, metformin users, thyroid hormone users, thyroid surgery patients, radioiodine users, pregnant people, and users of steroids were all disqualified. The study covered everyone who met the inclusion requirements during the study period. Clinical data were gathered using a

questionnaire that had been pre-structured. Baseline information was gathered, including age, a thorough medical history, prior events, family background, drug use history, and personal information. All subjects underwent a clinical examination as well as standard and pertinent investigations. According to the American Diabetic Association criteria or if the participants were already using diabetic medications, diabetes was determined to be present. Study Diabetic complications like retinopathy, ischemic heart disease, and nephropathy were examined in the subjects. After an overnight fast, venous blood samples were drawn from an arm's antecubital vein for analysis of the patient's lipid profile, 2-hour post-glucose blood sugar, and fasting blood sugar. Thyroid function is also assessed in venous blood (T3, T4, and TSH). Glucose oxidase-peroxidase was used to quantify plasma glucose concentration, and a one-step enzyme immunoassay was used to determine thyroid hormone levels. TSH levels below 10 mIU/L were deemed subclinical hypothyroidism, whereas levels above 10 mIU/L were deemed clinical hypothyroidism. The autoanalyzer was used to measure the levels of serum lipids (total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL cholesterol, and HDL plasma cholesterol). Chi-square test was employed to assess variations in categorical variables, and a statistically significant value of $p < 0.05$ was chosen.

Results

The study comprised 104 individuals with DM in total. When age and gender were connected with hypothyroidism in type 2 diabetics, the difference was statistically insignificant. Of them, 82.7% were euthyroid, 12.5% had subclinical hypothyroidism, and 4.8% had clinical hypothyroidism. In type 2 diabetics, there was a substantial correlation between dyslipidemia and hypothyroidism. Age-wise, 4.8% (5) of people with euthyroid

disease were in the 30–40 year age range, 27% (28) in the 41–50 year age range, 28.8% (30) in the 51–60 year age range, 20% (21) in the 61–70 year age range, and 1.9% (2) in the >71 year age range. In the subclinical category, 1.9% (2) of people in the 30–40 age range, 4.8% (5) in the 41–50

age range, 3.8% (4) in the 51–60 age range, and 1.9% (2) in the 61–70 age range. In the clinical category, there were 1.9% (2) in the group of people aged 51 to 60 and 1.9% (2) in the group of people aged 61 to 70. There was no statistically significant difference (Table 1).

Table 1: Age-wise thyroid function results among type 2 diabetes; n(%)

Age in years	Euthyroid	Subclinical	Clinical	Total
30-40	5 (4.8%)	2 (1.9%)	0	7 (6.7%)
41-50	28 (27%)	5 (4.8%)	1 (0.9%)	34 (32.7%)
51-60	30 (28.8%)	4 (3.8%)	2 (1.9%)	36 (34.6%)
61-70	21 (20%)	2 (1.9%)	2 (1.9%)	25 (24%)
>71	2 (1.9%)	0	0	2 (1.9%)
Total	86 (83.3%)	13 (12.5%)	5 (4.8%)	104 (100%)

Chi-Square: 3.727; df: 8, P = 0.881; statistically not significant

Among males, 5.8% had subclinical thyroid disease, 1.9% had clinical disease, and 32.6% (34) had euthyroid disease. In the female, 2.9% (3) was clinical, 6.7% (7) was subclinical, and 50% (52) were euthyroid. There was no statistically significant difference (Table 2).

Table 2: Gender-wise thyroid function results among type 2 diabetes; n(%)

Sex	Euthyroid	Subclinical	Clinical	Total
Male	34 (32.6%)	6 (5.8%)	2 (1.9%)	42 (40.4%)
Female	52 (50%)	7 (6.7%)	3 (2.9%)	62 (59.6%)
Total	86 (83.3%)	13 (12.5%)	5 (4.8%)	104 (100%)

Chi-Square: 0.206; df: 2, P = 0.902; statistically not significant

When thyroid test findings and dyslipidemia were associated, dyslipidemia was found in 32% of diabetics with normal thyroid function, 12.5% of subclinical cases, and 4.8% of clinical cases. In contrast, dyslipidemia was not seen in 51% of patients. There was a statistically significant difference (Table 3).

Table 3: Thyroid function results among type 2 diabetics with dyslipidemia; n(%)

Dyslipidemia	Euthyroid	Subclinical	Clinical	Total
Present	33 (32%)	13 (12.5%)	5 (4.8%)	51 (49%)
Absent	53 (51%)	0	0	53 (51%)
Total	86 (83.3%)	13 (12.5%)	5 (4.8%)	104 (100%)

Discussion

The largest cause of morbidity and mortality in the globe is diabetes. Its prevalence is seriously endangering public health because it is spreading around the globe on a daily basis. It is known that endocrine and nonendocrine organs besides the pancreas

might affect diabetes mellitus. Endocrine abnormalities of the thyroid are also quite prevalent in the general population. Consequently, it is typical for a person to have diabetes as well as thyroid problems. Worldwide, the prevalence is rising daily,

posing a serious threat to public health. The main changes in the thyroid hormone system are a decrease in the thyroid gland's activation by TSH, likely brought on by central hypothyroidism, and a decrease in the peripheral production of T3 from T4 [4-10]. Unrecognized thyroid dysfunction may worsen metabolic control and impede the management of diabetes. As a result, thyroid dysfunction in diabetic individuals needs to be screened [11].

The study focused on glycemic control and long-term consequences while simultaneously examining the prevalence of subclinical and clinical hypothyroidism in patients with type 2 diabetes. It also looked at how the length of diabetes influences the prevalence of hypothyroidism in type 2 diabetics. Out of 104 patients with type 2 diabetes in the current study, those between the ages of 41 and 70 had the highest prevalence of hypothyroidism. This suggests that the fourth and fifth decades of life were when the incidence peaked. Despite this incidence, age and hypothyroidism did not differ statistically significantly (Table 1; $P>0.05$).

Hypothyroidism was shown to be relatively common in type 2 DM patients older than 45 years in one retrospective research [12]. According to Telwani AA *et al.*, hypothyroidism is more prevalent in people over 50 [1] Significant changes are made to the control of glucose homeostasis by thyroid hormones. Intestinal absorption, hepatic synthesis, changes in circulating insulin levels and counter-regulatory hormones, and peripheral organs' uptake of glucose are among these impacts [13].

In this investigation, thyroid defects were reported in 7.7% of males and 9.6% of females, respectively; statistically, there was no gender difference (Table 2; $P>0.05$). According to a study by Udiong CEJ, male diabetics had lower levels of TSH than non-diabetics and their TSH levels was lower

overall [6]. Another study from India found that the occurrence of thyroid disorders was particularly high in females, with rates of 36% and 22%, respectively, and higher rates among older people (those older than 60 years) [14]. According to epidemiological research, the prevalence of overt and subclinical hypothyroidism was higher in women over 60 years old and ranged from 2-4% to 4-20%, respectively [15,16]. An autoimmune mechanism most usually causes hypothyroidism or overactive thyroid. More than 40 million Indians have thyroid issues, according to a report [17].

Recent investigations have shown that diabetics have a higher frequency of thyroid dysfunction than the general population. According to population research, women over the age of 60 are substantially more likely to have overt hypothyroidism or its subclinical symptoms, which vary from 2-4% to 4-20%, respectively [16]. The clinical condition of hypothyroidism is brought on by a decrease in the secretion of the thyroid hormones thyroxine and triiodothyronine, or, very rarely, by a decrease in the action of these hormones in the tissues.

The grade of primary hypothyroidism with high thyroid-stimulating hormone levels and normal serum free thyroxine and triiodothyronine concentrations is referred to as "subclinical hypothyroidism." About 2-5% of cases each year of subclinical hypothyroidism may escalate to overt hypothyroidism. Treatment is recommended for all patients with TSH > 10 mIU/L who have overt hypothyroidism or subclinical hypothyroidism [18]. While hypothyroidism results in decreased glucose oxidation, hyperthyroidism induces lipid peroxidation. LDL clearance lowers triglyceride and cholesterol levels.

T3 is known to increase levels of fasting plasma glucose and free fatty acids [19]. In the current investigation, patients with euthyroid, subclinical, and clinical

hypothyroidism were found to have dyslipidemia in 32%, 12.5%, and 4.8% of participants, respectively. This statistical difference was significant (Table 3; $P < 0.05$). A significant percentage of severe clinical hypothyroidism (SCH) was also noted in the literature [20]. Although it is debatable if SCH is the main cause of the high prevalence of CHD, these alterations may show that elevated TSH can have an impact on blood lipids and the vascular endothelium in people with Type 2 diabetes. In contrast, a cross-sectional study found that 95.5% of type 2 DM had dyslipidemia [21-23].

Conclusion

According to this study results and the literature that is currently available, type 2 DM patients with hypothyroidism are highly common. Thyroid hormones, however, have significant impacts on gluconeogenesis, delayed peripheral glucose buildup, decreased hepatic glucose production, and reduced glucose excretion. It follows that both can enhance other metabolisms.

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